

1 **Seasonal variations of sinking velocities in Austral diatom blooms: Lessons learned from**
2 **COMICS**

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10
11 **ABSTRACT**

12 The sinking velocity (SV) of organic particles is a critical driver of carbon transport to the deep
13 sea. Accurate determination of marine particle SV and their influencing factors is therefore a key
14 to better understanding of biological carbon storage in the ocean. We used two different
15 approaches to estimate average SVs of particles during a Southern Ocean spring bloom (North
16 of South Georgia): optical backscatter sensors on gliders (“large”, >50 µm diameter), and
17 radioactive pairs (²³⁴Th-²³⁸U and ²¹⁰Po-²¹⁰Pb). Our results were complemented with time-of flight
18 estimations of bulk SVs from deep sediment traps deployed at 1950 m.

19 Bulk SVs increased consistently with depth from 15 ± 1 m d⁻¹ at 10 m to 50 ± 10 m d⁻¹ at the
20 depth of export ($Z_p = 95$ m) and from 96 ± 35 m d⁻¹ at 150 m to $119 \pm$ m d⁻¹ at 450 m. Only the
21 fastest particles, mainly comprised by faecal pellets (FPs) and diatom aggregates, survived
22 remineralization and dominated carbon fluxes at deep depth.

23 The SV variability at the base of the Euphotic Zone was studied in relation to the stage of the
24 bloom by analysing three different moments of the spring diatom bloom in the region during the
25 years 2012, 2013 and 2017. The export efficiency (*ExpEff*), defined as the ratio POC flux
26 exported below the Euphotic Zone to the satellite derived surface NPP, was also evaluated. It
27 was found from the temporal series that *ExpEff* and SV vary throughout the diatom bloom as the
28 community structure progresses. A good correlation between both variables was observed
29 ($ExpEff = (0.023 \pm 0.006) SV$, $r = 0.82$, $p = 0.04$). Showing that the variability in how efficiently
30 the carbon flux is exported out of the Euphotic Zone can be explained by the SV at which the
31 particles sink. Further investigations are required to analyse if this is a specific model of the
32 functioning of the BCP during the diatom bloom in North South Georgia or if it can be
33 extrapolated to other scenarios.

34
35 **KEY WORDS:** particle sinking velocity, ²¹⁰Po, ²³⁴Th, gliders, deep sediment traps,
36 transfer efficiency, export efficiency, carbon attenuation.

38 1. INTRODUCTION

39 Sinking particles constitute one of the main mechanisms of the Biological Carbon Pump (BCP)
40 (Fowler and Knauer, 1986) and are a major pathway of carbon from the surface into the deep
41 ocean, exporting 5-20 Gt C every year (Henson et al., 2011). Sinking particles are a complex mix
42 of biogeochemical materials, and differ in their size, density, porosity, morphology, and hence
43 sinking velocity (SV). The magnitude of the downward flux by sinking particles depends mainly
44 on the production rate of the particles, the velocity and carbon content of these particles, and the
45 rates at which this material is fragmented or biologically consumed (i.e. the remineralization rate)
46 (De La Rocha and Passow, 2007). Accurate estimation of these rates is hence of great value for
47 advancing understanding of the global ocean carbon sink and its variability.

48 Below the Euphotic Zone, the variation of sinking carbon flux is determined by the balance
49 between particle remineralization rate and SV (Sarmiento and Gruber, 2006). How these two
50 rates vary and interact spatiotemporally is not fully understood (Cram et al., 2018; Henson et al.,
51 2012; Le Moigne et al., 2013), partly because both rates are highly variable (Buesseler and Boyd,
52 2009; Cavan et al., 2017; De La Rocha and Passow, 2007; Iversen and Ploug, 2013; Villa-
53 Alfageme et al., 2016a; Wiedmann et al., 2014), their measurements are intrinsically complex,
54 and few data are available. Moreover, both rates are coupled: SV depend on size, composition
55 and shape, which are typically altered as particles are being remineralized.

56 SV is included in a range of models, including ecological (e.g. Yool et al., 2013), stochastic (e.g.
57 de Soto et al., 2018; Jokulsdottir and Archer, 2016), mechanistic (e.g. Cram et al., 2018; DeVries
58 et al., 2014; DeVries and Weber, 2017) and regional Lagrangian models (e.g. Aumont et al.,
59 2015). While some mechanistic flux models include different approaches to parameterize particle
60 SVs and remineralisation in order to more accurately describe dynamic biological processes (De
61 Soto et al., 2018; DeVries, 2014; Jokulsdottir and Archer, 2016; Omand et al., 2020), the
62 parameterization of SV in global ocean models usually does not reflect its temporal and global
63 variability (e.g. Aumont et al., 2015; DeVries and Weber, 2017).

64 It is not easy to obtain an accurate determination of *in situ* SV (e.g. Giering et al., 2020). SV can
65 be measured in the laboratory (e.g. Bach et al., 2012; Laurenceau-Cornec et al., 2020; van der
66 Jagt et al., 2018; Zetsche et al., 2020) and in the field using particle settling velocity traps (IRS-
67 ST) (Alonso-Gonzalez et al., 2010) or imaging analyses of particles collected on gel sediment
68 traps (McDonnell and Buesseler, 2012). A significant step forward in the evaluation of SV are
69 techniques based on underwater camera imaging (e.g. Giering et al., 2020; Guidi et al., 2008;
70 Iversen et al., 2010; Kiko et al., 2017). These methods have in common that the individual SV
71 of a set of single particles is tracked directly in field or laboratory settings. The bulk SV is then
72 obtained by either extrapolation or estimating particle distributions (Guidi et al., 2008). An
73 alternative is to use methods that estimate *in situ* bulk SV directly, such as gliders (Briggs et al.)
74 or radioactive pairs (Villa-Alfageme et al., 2014), which track the signal left by the particles as
75 they sink.

76 Here, we synthesise *in situ* bulk SV measurements during the peak and decline of the
77 phytoplankton bloom north of South Georgia, a naturally iron-fertilized region downstream of

78 the island. This work is part of the COMICS (Controls over Ocean Mesopelagic Carbon Storage)
79 project (Sanders et al., 2016). Average particle SV throughout the upper 500 m of the water
80 column were obtained from radioactive tracer pairs ^{210}Po - ^{210}Pb and from plume-tracking on
81 glider-derived optical backscatter. In addition, we calculated the bulk SV of a pulse of particles
82 sinking from the base of the Euphotic Zone to a deep sediment trap located at 1950 m depth. We
83 discuss how SV related to export rates and how they vary with community structure, depth, stage
84 of the bloom or other factors.

85

86 2. SAMPLING AND METHODS

87 2.1. Site description

88 The region downstream of South Georgia was sampled in Nov/Dec 2017 on board RRS
89 Discovery (cruise DY086) as part of the UK COMICS programme (Sanders et al., 2016). Station
90 P3 (52°24 S, 40°04 W) (Figure 1), close to British Antarctic Survey's mooring, was extensively
91 sampled three times in cycles of ~1 week each: P3A (15 November – 22 November, DOY 319-
92 326), P3B (29 November – 5 December, DOY 333-339) and P3C (9 December – 15 December,
93 DOY 343-349). P3 is located in the Northern South Georgia region, which is characterised by
94 annual large phytoplankton blooms fertilized by iron from the islands nearby (Robinson et al.,
95 2016). The iron is introduced to the water column by the Subantarctic Circumpolar Current Front,
96 leading to the increased diatom productivity downstream of South Georgia (Jones et al., 2012;
97 Korb et al., 2012, 2010). In this region, the phytoplankton growth season is long, and blooms
98 usually persist for more than four months (Atkinson et al., 2001). Our cruise followed a rapidly-
99 changing diatom spring bloom from peak to decline.

100

101 2.2. Radioactive pair disequilibrium (^{210}Po - ^{210}Pb and ^{234}Th - ^{238}U)

102 2.2.1. Particle organic carbon (POC) export flux from radionuclide pairs

103 The methods to calculate POC downward flux from POC- ^{210}Po and POC- ^{234}Th are well
104 established (Ceballos-Romero et al., 2016; Le Moigne et al., 2013; Verdeny et al., 2009) and are
105 based on the disequilibrium in the activity concentration of the radioactive daughter (^{210}Po and
106 ^{234}Th) and its radioactive parent (^{210}Pb and ^{238}U). A disequilibrium appears when the particle-
107 reactive radionuclide, either ^{210}Po ($T_{1/2} = 138$ days) or ^{234}Th ($T_{1/2} = 24$ days), is scavenged from
108 the water column by sinking particles. For ^{210}Po and ^{234}Th downward flux, the radioactive
109 disequilibrium is converted into flux using a one-box model (Savoie et al., 2006). Assuming
110 steady state and negligible advection effects downward flux, P , is obtained following,

$$111 P = \lambda_2 \sum_{z=0}^{z=h} (A_2^{total} - A_1^{total}) \Delta z \quad (1),$$

112 where A_1^{total} is the total parent activity concentration for ^{238}U or ^{210}Pb ; A_2^{total} is the total ^{234}Th
113 or ^{210}Po activity concentration and λ_2 is the decay constant of the daughter. The tracer flux P is
114 then converted into POC downward flux, POC_{flux} , by applying the measured ratio ($Q_{>53}$) of POC-
115 to-radionuclide (POC: ^{210}Po or POC: ^{234}Th) in large ($>53 \mu\text{m}$) particles:

116 $POC_{flux} = P \cdot Q_{>53}$ (2).

117 Uncertainties in $Q_{>53}$ for ^{210}Po and ^{234}Th were obtained directly from error propagation applied
 118 to the counting uncertainty (using $\pm \sigma$ of number of counts), volume and tracer uncertainties.

119 Both radionuclides present very different half-lives, that have implications specially in the
 120 interpretation of results during a non-steady state situation.

121

122 2.2.2. Sinking velocity from radionuclide pairs

123 The methods to calculate SV using the radioactive pair disequilibrium are relatively novel (Villa-
 124 Alfageme et al., 2014), and a full description of the method is presented elsewhere (Villa-
 125 Alfageme et al., 2016a, 2014). In brief, as explained above, the disequilibrium ^{234}Th - ^{238}U and
 126 ^{210}Po - ^{210}Pb emerges when ^{234}Th or ^{210}Po is scavenged from the water column by particles sinking
 127 at different velocities. This way, ^{210}Po or ^{234}Th flux, P , is generated by the sinking particles and
 128 thus average particle SV at specific depths can be diagnosed from,

129 $P(Bq\ m^{-2}\ s^{-1}) = SV(m\ s^{-1}) \cdot A_2^{part}(Bq\ m^{-3})$ (3),

130 where A_{T2}^{part} is the activity concentration of ^{234}Th or ^{210}Po in the particulate fraction at that depth.

131 We have implemented a method applying an inverse model to Eq (1) to estimate which average
 132 bulk SV is responsible for the observed parent-daughter disequilibrium. Eq. (1) is rearranged to
 133 include δ , the fitting parameter in our inverse model, and it is combined with Eq. (3) as,

134 $A_1^{total}(z) \cdot \lambda_2 - A_2^{total}(z) \cdot \lambda_2 - \lambda_{Th} \frac{d(\delta \cdot A_2^{total})}{dz} = 0$ (4),

135 where δ corresponds to,

136 $\delta(z) = SV \cdot \frac{A_2^{part}}{\lambda_2} \frac{1}{A_2^{total}}$ (5).

137 SV is obtained from fitting δ . A confidence interval for each fitting δ of the inverse model was
 138 estimated from the difference between modelled and measured ^{210}Po concentrations, and
 139 subsequent error propagation was used to calculate the uncertainties.

140

141 2.2.3. Sampling and ^{210}Po and ^{210}Pb analysis during COMICS I

142 Total ^{210}Po and ^{210}Pb activities were determined using the coprecipitation with iron (Villa-
 143 Alfageme et al., 2016b). Three vertical profiles (one during each visit: P3A, P3B and P3C) of 5-
 144 L seawater samples were collected from 10 to 1000 m using Niskin bottles attached to a CTD
 145 rosette, with higher vertical sampling resolution in the upper 150 m of the water column (Figure
 146 S1, Supplementary Material). Samples were immediately acidified and spiked with stable Pb and
 147 ^{209}Po as chemical yield tracers and Fe^{3+} for subsequent coprecipitation of $\text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$ by raising the
 148 pH using NH_4OH . Iron hydroxide was collected by siphoning the remaining water and stored
 149 for processing on land. The coprecipitate was digested with HNO_3 and samples were re-dissolved
 150 with 1 M HCl . ^{210}Po and ^{209}Po were selectively auto-deposited onto silver discs during 12 h. The
 151 silver discs were counted by alpha-spectrometry using passivated implanted planar silicon (PIPS)

152 alpha detectors (Canberra, USA). Solutions were replated. Samples were re-spiked with ^{209}Po
153 and stored for 9–11 months for later determination of ^{210}Pb via ^{210}Po ingrowth. At that time,
154 samples were plated and counted once more by alpha-spectrometry. ^{210}Pb and ^{210}Po activities at
155 sampling time were calculated by applying in-growth, decay, and recovery corrections (Ceballos-
156 Romero et al., 2016).

157 Large ($>53\ \mu\text{m}$) and small ($<53\ \mu\text{m}$) particles were collected using stand-alone *in situ* pumps
158 (SAPS, Challenger Oceanic, UK). SAPS were deployed at 4 depths from 25 m to 450 m, filtering
159 on average 1500 L over 2 hours. Particles retained on the 53- μm pore size nylon mesh screens
160 were rinsed into a bottle using filtered seawater, homogenized and subdivided into six aliquots
161 using a splitter. One aliquot was filtered through QMA filters for analysis of ^{210}Po and ^{210}Pb . Any
162 zooplankton observed on the filters (by naked eye) were removed using forceps. The filters were
163 then spiked with ^{209}Po and stable Pb, digested using a mixture of concentrated HNO_3 (3 mL),
164 HCl (1 mL), and HF (0.5 mL), dried and re-dissolved with 1 M HCl . Samples were then analysed
165 using alpha-spectrometry as described for the water samples. One aliquot was filtered onto pre-
166 combusted and weighted GF/F filters for particulate organic carbon (POC), dried and analysed
167 using by mass evaluation after combustion (Le Moigne et al., 2013).

168

169 **2.3. Sinking velocity from optical sensors on gliders during COMICS I**

170 Three high-resolution underwater gliders surveyed a triangle with sides of ~ 12 km, centred on
171 $52^\circ 45$ S, $40^\circ 26$ W, with its southernmost vertex 2 km north of the British Antarctic Survey's P3
172 mooring, ($52^\circ 24$ S, $40^\circ 04$ W) as part of the sister project GOCART (Gauging ocean Organic
173 Carbon fluxes using Autonomous Robotic Technologies, Henson et al., this issue). During 2017
174 austral spring, a Seaglider, belonging to CSIR (South Africa), was deployed on the DOY 292
175 and recovered on DOY 365. Two Slocum gliders (G2s type), belonging to NOC (UK), were
176 deployed on DOY 323 and DOY 326 and both recovered on DOY 44 from 2018. All gliders
177 measured temperature, salinity and dissolved oxygen concentration (Henson et al., this issue).
178 They were further fitted with a custom-made Wetlabs Environmental Characterization (ECO)
179 Triplet, measuring backscatter (at 532 and 700 nm) and chlorophyll fluorescence. The gliders
180 were programmed to profile between 0 and 1000 m, with each dive cycle taking ~ 5 h to complete
181 and covering an average horizontal distance of 4 km.

182 High-resolution vertical profiles of large and small particles were calculated following the
183 method by Briggs et al. (2011). Briefly, a minimum-maximum filter isolates spikes (i.e. 'large
184 particles') from a baseline signal (i.e. 'small particles'). The size of 'large particles' was
185 estimated to be $>420\ \mu\text{m}$ in diameter (Henson et al., this issue). We then calculated the bulk SV
186 of these large particles using a modification of the plume tracking (Briggs et al., 2020a). Five
187 plumes were identified between DOY 323 and DOY 347 and tracked both visually and using a
188 statistical approach. Two of these plumes also showed a strong signal in the small particles, so
189 the plume tracking was performed for both particle size classes, providing SVs for both large and
190 small particles. Detailed descriptions of the method and POC flux profiles are provided by
191 Henson et al. (this issue) and Giering et al. (this issue).

192

193 **2.4. Net primary productivity and export efficiency**

194 The 8-day satellite-derived net primary production (NPP) data with a spatial resolution of 0.083
195 by 0.083° were obtained from the Oregon State University Ocean Productivity standard products
196 (<http://www.science.oregonstate.edu/ocean.productivity/>), wherein NPP was estimated by the
197 Vertically Generalized Production Model (VGPM) (Behrenfeld and Falkowski, 1997). Satellite-
198 derived NPP values agreed with glider-derived primary production estimates for our cruise
199 period (Henson et al., this issue), which was obtained by following the approach of Mignot et al.
200 (2018).

201 Export Efficiency (*ExpEff*) was defined as the ratio of POC export flux at the base of the export
202 zone (Z_p), in our case derived from the radioactive pairs, to NPP. Due to the persistence of the
203 radioactive disequilibrium in the water for more than three weeks for ^{234}Th - ^{238}U and more than
204 six weeks for ^{210}Po - ^{210}Pb , NPP was calculated in two ways: by integrating the data from (i) the
205 three weeks previous to the sampling, and (ii) if during three weeks previous to the sampling, the
206 blooms, the integration would include only the days of the bloom.

207 The export depth was defined as the base of the productive layer (Z_p), which is the layer in which
208 particles can be produced photosynthetically. Hence, Z_p denotes the depth that separates euphotic
209 and mesopelagic zone. The estimates of Z_p used here were the ones calculated for our cruise
210 (Giering et al., this issue). Briefly, Z_p was calculated from the glider time-series (Henson et al.,
211 this issue) following the latest recommendations by Buesseler et al. (2020) and using a
212 modification of the metric by Owens et al. (2015). For each glider profile, Z_p was defined as the
213 deepest point at which Chl was higher than 10% of the maximum Chl concentration for that
214 profile. The resulting Z_p s were $92.5 \text{ m} \pm 8.1 \text{ m}$, $91.5 \text{ m} \pm 12.9 \text{ m}$ and $88.5 \text{ m} \pm 10.4 \text{ m}$ for P3A,
215 P3B and P3C, respectively. As the glider-derived high-resolution POC concentrations and fluxes
216 were binned in 10-m bins, a nominal value of 95 m (i.e. encompassing fluxes between 90 and
217 100 m) was thus used as export depth for all visits.

218

219 **2.5. Time-of-flight estimation of bulk SV using a deep sediment trap during COMICS I**

220 A sediment trap (McLane Parflux sediment trap, 0.5 m² surface collecting area; McLane Labs,
221 Falmouth, MA, USA) was deployed on the mooring at P3 as part of the Ecosystems programme
222 and the Scotia Sea Open Ocean Laboratories (SCOOBIES) sustained observation programme at
223 the British Antarctic Survey. The trap contained a carousel of 21 receiving cups and was fitted
224 with a plastic baffle mounted on the opening to prevent the entrance of large organisms.

225 During COMICS I, the sediment trap was deployed at 1950 m and the carousel programmed to
226 rotate every 5 days over a 105-day period between mid-October 2017 and late January 2018,
227 covering the spring bloom period during our cruise. A complete description and discussion of
228 the mooring and observed POC flux at 1950 m is provided by Manno et al. (this issue).

229 Using a ‘time-of-flight approach’ (Armstrong et al., 2009; Mas et al., 2020), we estimated the
230 velocity at which temporal patterns in flux propagated between the Z_p and the deep sediment trap
231 located at 1950 m depth. The range of SV of the particles that produced the peak of export can
232 be obtained from the time elapsed between the maximum in POC export flux and the moment
233 this peak is detected by the deep sediment trap. As detailed in section 3.1, in 2017 a peak in the
234 carbon was detected by the gliders at the Z_p (DOY 319) and an intense peak in carbon export was
235 collected in the deep sediment trap at 1950 m 17 days later (DOY 336). To estimate the bulk SV
236 of these sinking particles, we used the distance between POC flux export peak (DOY 319 at 95
237 m) and deep-sediment trap fluxes (DOY 336 at 1950 m) and the time elapsed between them.
238 Thus, a time-of-flight approach was followed, using 17 days as elapsed time and the 1855 m
239 distance between both detections.

240

241 **2.6. NPP, deep sediment traps and sinking velocity during 2012 and 2013**

242 To obtain additional information of the variables analysed for P3 during COMICS I spring
243 bloom, NPP, *ExpEff* and particle average SV were also evaluated for the years 2012 and 2013
244 using ^{234}Th - ^{238}U and ^{210}Po - ^{210}Pb disequilibrium values from previous cruises. In line with our
245 cruise, the Z_p was assumed to be 95 m. All measurements were taken in the proximities of the P3
246 station. For 2012, ^{234}Th - ^{238}U data were collected during cruise JR274 (Le Moigne et al. (2014)).
247 For 2013, ^{210}Po - ^{210}Po and ^{234}Th - ^{238}U data were collected during the Western Core Box survey
248 JCR291 (Ceballos-Romero et al. (2022)). For both cruises, average SV and *ExpEff* were obtained
249 as described in the methods section, together with the satellite derived NPP. As the austral bloom
250 ranges from October to February, for every bloom we included results from October to December
251 (DOY from 250 to 365) of the year and from January to March of following year (DOY from 1
252 to 85).

253 Deep sediment traps were also deployed by the British Antarctic Survey between 2012 and 2014.
254 The traps collected downward sinking material at ~1950 m with a periodicity of 1 month (Figure
255 3) from 1st December 2012 to 1st January 2014. According to the corresponding NPP profiles,
256 the material collected in January during the 2012-2013 deployment (Figure 3) corresponded to
257 the end of 2012 austral bloom, whereas material collected at the end of 2013 during the 2013-
258 2014 deployment (Figure 3) corresponded to material from the austral bloom of 2013.

259

260 **3. RESULTS**

261 **3.1. NPP and POC fluxes at 1950 m depth during COMICS I**

262 Our cruise captured the peak and decline of a spring bloom as shown by satellite-derived (Figure
263 2) and glider-derived NPP (Henson et al., this issue). Based on satellite-derived NPP estimates,
264 NPP started to increase in mid-September with an initial short-lived bloom ($\sim 1400 \text{ mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$)
265 in early October. NPP steadily increased until the start of our cruise, where NPP peaked again
266 at $\sim 1400 \text{ mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ (mid-November; P3A) before it steadily decreased during our cruise to
267 $\sim 550 \text{ mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ (mid-December; P3C). After we left the site, a third and more pronounced

268 bloom occurred around mid-January to early February with satellite-derived NPP rates as high
269 as $2600 \text{ mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$. Glider-derived NPP data shows the same temporal trend, though the
270 absolute magnitude of the three bloom peaks was ~ 1600 , ~ 2000 and $\sim 1900 \text{ mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ (Henson
271 et al., this issue).

272 The deep sediment trap (1950 m depth) appeared to have captured the first, short-lived bloom
273 (mid-September) in early November (DOY 311), with fluxes as high as $25 \text{ mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ (Figure
274 3) and mainly comprised of faecal pellets (60% of the total POC flux) and fresh single cell
275 diatoms (39%) (Manno et al., this issue). The second bloom (mid-November), which concurred
276 with P3A, appeared to have been captured by the deep sediment trap in early December. This
277 second deep-flux peak was comprised of fast sinking zooplankton faecal pellets (66% of the total
278 POC flux), lowly-sinking partially remineralized diatom aggregates and phytodetritus (28%), and
279 single-cell diatoms (5%) (Manno et al., this issue).

280

281 **3.2. ^{210}Po -derived POC fluxes during COMICS I**

282 During both P3A and P3C, ^{210}Po -derived POC fluxes increased with depth throughout the
283 productive layer, reaching a maximum at Z_p ($\sim 95 \text{ m}$; i.e. ‘export flux’) with 360 ± 100 and 350
284 $\pm 100 \text{ mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$, respectively (Figure 4, Table 1). Below the Z_p , ^{210}Po -derived POC fluxes
285 decreased to minima of $200 \text{ mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ and $0 \text{ mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ at 350 m depth during P3A and P3C,
286 respectively. During P3B, ^{210}Po -derived POC fluxes steadily increased from the surface to 250
287 m depth (maximum: $350 \text{ mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$). ^{210}Po -derived export flux during P3B was $153 \pm 39 \text{ mg}$
288 $\text{C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$. Our ^{210}Po -derived export flux estimates fall within the range of the glider-derived export
289 flux estimates (Table 1; Henson et al., this issue), though are on the lower end (mean glider-
290 derived POC export during P3A, P3B and P3C, respectively: $646, 409, 287 \text{ mg C m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$; Giering
291 et al., this issue). As the glider fluxes were calibrated using independent flux measurements (e.g.
292 Marine Snow Catcher) (Giering et al., this issue), we speculate that the ^{210}Po -derived POC fluxes
293 underestimated true fluxes owing to the non-steady state assumption. Although the steady-state
294 assumption is widely applied to most methods for obtaining fluxes or SV, it can introduce a
295 systematic bias (Ceballos-Romero et al., 2018; Giering et al., 2017). In addition, there are
296 temporal mismatches between both (1) flux estimates using gliders, marine snow catchers and
297 radiotracers, and (2) between the radiotracer in sinking particles (instantaneously collected to
298 estimate POC/ ^{210}Po ratio) and water (^{210}Po flux is associated to ^{210}Po radioactive half-life of 138
299 days). The non-steady state conditions during our cruise likely introduced uncertainties in the
300 interpretation of radiotracer disequilibria as, when export increased at the beginning of the cruise,
301 the radioactive disequilibrium would not have appeared instantaneously in the water column,
302 rather it would have been delayed by a few days (Ceballos-Romero et al., 2018). Conversely,
303 when export decreased, the disequilibrium would have been maintained for a few days after. As
304 a result, during the bloom, as a general rule, the radiotracer approach underestimates POC flux
305 at the beginning and overestimates it at the end of the bloom (Ceballos-Romero et al., 2018).

306 An additional source of inaccuracy might overcome due to an under collection of ^{210}Po from the
307 water in relation to the ^{209}Po internal tracer used to quantify the extraction yield (Roca-Martí et

308 al., 2021). This can sometimes produce a small underestimation of ^{210}Po concentrations that
309 would result in overestimated fluxes. As ^{210}Po -derived POC fluxes here are in the lowest range
310 of all the used techniques during COMICS I, it is unlikely to expect overestimated ^{210}Po -derived
311 POC fluxes due to under collection of ^{210}Po in the sampling process.

312

313 **3.3. Sinking velocities during COMICS I**

314 ^{210}Po - derived SV increased with depth for all profiles from $\sim 15 \text{ m d}^{-1}$ at the surface to $>100 \text{ m}$
315 d^{-1} in the upper mesopelagic zone (Figure 5). In the upper 100 m, estimated SV were the same
316 for all three visits (within their uncertainties). For P3A and P3B, from approximately 15 m d^{-1} in
317 surface waters to 185 m d^{-1} at 150 m and 110 m d^{-1} at 250 m. During P3C, ^{210}Po - derived SV in
318 the upper 100 m were the same as during P3A and P3B considering their uncertainties and
319 compared to the standard deviation of the three values at each depth. However, at and below 150
320 m, the SVs during P3C were considerably slower ($\sim 50 \text{ m d}^{-1}$) than those for P3A and P3B (110 -
321 186 m d^{-1}) (Figure 5; Table 1).

322 Glider-derived SV estimates were $\sim 60 \text{ m d}^{-1}$ at 140, $80 - 130 \text{ m d}^{-1}$ at 250 m, and 130 m d^{-1} at
323 460 m (average values $70 \pm 20 \text{ m d}^{-1}$, $100 \pm 25 \text{ m d}^{-1}$, $120 \pm 10 \text{ m d}^{-1}$ at the depths 155 m, 250
324 and 490 m) (Figure 5; Table 1), with no clear differences observed between the visits (Table 1)
325 according to SV uncertainties and standard deviation.

326 Both approaches to estimate SV, ^{210}Po - ^{210}Pb disequilibrium and the glider-derived backscatter,
327 provide bulk-average estimates. The main difference between the two methods is that, whereas
328 the glider derives SV estimates for particles of two sizes (~ 100 - $400 \mu\text{m}$ for the small particles
329 peak and $> 400 \mu\text{m}$ for the large particles peak), the ^{210}Po - ^{210}Pb disequilibrium is not associated
330 to any particle size and thus represents all sinking particles. Moreover, while the glider-based
331 method takes advantage of non-steady-state conditions (i.e. plume tracking), the radionuclide
332 approach assumes steady state (as for the flux calculations). Despite these differences, the SV
333 estimates from the gliders and from the radionuclides agree well with each other (within
334 uncertainties; Figure 5a).

335 For the depth-averaged profile, we binned the depth 10 m, 50 m, 75-100 m (nominal: 90 m), 140-
336 175 m (nominal: 150 m), and 350 - 520 m (nominal: 442 m), and obtained the maximum,
337 minimum and average values of the $\text{SV}_{\text{binned}}$ estimates for these depths (including both
338 radionuclide- and glider-derived values).

339 The $\text{SV}_{\text{binned}}$ increased from $50 \pm 10 \text{ m d}^{-1}$ at Z_p to $100 \pm 50 \text{ m d}^{-1}$ (150 m) (Figure 5b). Minimum
340 and maximum $\text{SV}_{\text{binned}}$ estimates in the dataset also increased with depth: for minima from 35 m
341 d^{-1} at Z_p (95 m) to 110 m d^{-1} (440 m), and for maxima from 70 m d^{-1} at Z_p to 130 m d^{-1} at 440 m.
342 The depth-averaged vertical profile of both methods showed a rapid linear increase in $\text{SV}_{\text{binned}}$ in
343 the upper 150 m at a rate of $0.6 [\text{m d}^{-1}] \text{ m}^{-1}$ (linear regression: $R^2 = 0.99$; $t = 11.5$, $p = 0.001$, $n =$
344 4). Below 150, average $\text{SV}_{\text{binned}}$ continued to increase albeit at a slower rate of $0.1 [\text{m d}^{-1}] \text{ m}^{-1}$
345 (linear regression: $R^2 = 0.96$; $t = 4.4$, $p = 0.05$; $n = 3$). When the increase is examined using the
346 individual SV data (i.e. Figure 5a), the increase in SV in the upper 150 m is statistically

347 significant ($R^2 = 0.68$; $t = 3.4$, $p = 0.005$, $n = 15$) but not statistically significant below 150 m (R^2
348 $= 0.24$; $t = 0.9$, $p = 0.38$, $n = 15$).

349 Bulk SVs of particles contributing to POC flux at 1950 m, evaluated using the time-of-flight
350 approach, ranged from 84 – 109 $m\ d^{-1}$ (Figure 5a) depending on the applied time window (export
351 date between DOY 314 - 319, and particle collection between DOY 336 - 358). This bulk SV
352 estimate agrees well with the estimates from the gliders and radionuclide pairs.

353

354 **3.4. NPP and sinking velocities at P3 during 2012 and 2013 spring blooms**

355 In 2012, 2013 and 2017, P3 was sampled during different stages of the diatom bloom. 2017
356 captured the peak of the bloom and its subsequent declining; 2013 sampling cruise took place
357 after the peak, when the bloom was already declining; and 2012 captured the end of a spring
358 bloom. In terms of NPP, the 2012 bloom was very intense, reaching 2500 $mg\ C\ m^{-2}\ d^{-1}$ during
359 the peak (Figure 2). At the end of the bloom, when the ^{234}Th samples were taken, NPP dropped
360 below 1000 $mg\ C\ m^{-2}\ d^{-1}$. NPP in 2013 was generally low, with a peak of 850 $mg\ C\ m^{-2}\ d^{-1}$. In
361 contrast, the spring bloom during 2017 was relatively intense in November, with a peak in NPP
362 of approximately 1400 $mg\ C\ m^{-2}\ d^{-1}$.

363 In 2017 (peak of bloom), SVs at the Z_p were 44 - 58 $m\ d^{-1}$. In 2013 (after bloom peak), SVs were
364 variable at Z_p (46 - 225 $m\ d^{-1}$, average 140 $m\ d^{-1}$) but generally the highest of all SV estimates
365 for P3 (Figure 2). In 2012 (post-bloom), SV were the slowest with 24 – 38 $m\ d^{-1}$ (average 31 m
366 d^{-1}).

367

368 **3.5. Relationship between SV and Export Efficiency**

369 For the peak bloom phase (2017), our estimates of export efficiency ($ExpEff$) were moderate
370 (15-30%) and slightly lower than gliders' estimates (Henson et al., this issue) (Figure 6). In the
371 early post-bloom period (2013), we observed the highest $ExpEff$ (20 - 50%). And during the late
372 post-bloom phase (2012), $ExpEff$ were lowest (7 - 8%). We found a significant linear correlation
373 between $ExpEff$ and SV ($ExpEff = (0.023 \pm 0.006) SV$, $R = 0.82$, $p = 0.04$, $n = 9$) (Figure 6).

374

375 **4. DISCUSSION**

376 **4.1. Sinking velocity rates in COMICS I**

377 Our bulk SV estimates using the radiotracers, gliders and time-of-flight approaches agreed well,
378 suggesting that our estimates are reliable. Further, our estimates (40-190 $m\ d^{-1}$ between 150 –
379 400 m depth) are consistent with ^{210}Po -derived SV estimates across the North Atlantic (30 – 300
380 $m\ d^{-1}$; Villa-Alfageme et al., 2016a) and autonomous float-based estimates from the North
381 Atlantic and Southern Ocean (58 – 129 $m\ d^{-1}$; Briggs et al., 2020b).

382 Our bulk SV from all depths span the same range as independent in-situ particle-specific SV
383 estimates from cameras mounted on the PELAGRA sediment traps at 500 m ($66 \pm 47\ m\ d^{-1}$ for
384 particles with a diameter of 0.5-2.3 mm) (Iversen, personal communication). These values are

385 similar to *in situ* SVs of individual particles derived by combining viscous polyacrylamide gels
386 and camera imaging along the west Antarctica Peninsula (10-150 m d⁻¹ for particles with a
387 diameter of 0.1-2.0 mm; McDonnell and Buesseler, 2010). However, they are slower than those
388 observed during a North Atlantic diatom spring bloom: particle-specific SVs, measured using
389 cameras mounted on Lagrangian sediment traps at variable depths in the Euphotic Zone during
390 the summer months, were on average 156 ± 98 m d⁻¹ for particles with a diameter of 0.1 to 1.9
391 mm (Iversen and Lampitt, 2020). Overall, the camera-based particle-specific SVs were on the
392 lower end of the bulk velocities at depth (Figure 5). This discrepancy could indicate a bias in our
393 deep (300-500 m) bulk SV estimates, which are fewer and more uncertain than our shallower
394 estimates. However, it is more likely caused by the different temporal resolution and target size
395 of the two methods, with radiotracers capturing SV over several days and across all particle sizes
396 whereas camera systems take snap-shot samples of a relatively narrow particle size range. As the
397 spatiotemporal coverage of the camera-based estimates is much lower than our bulk SV
398 estimates, the discrepancy near 500 m may simply indicate spatiotemporal variability in mean
399 SV at a given depth over the course of the spring phytoplankton bloom.

400

401 **4.2. Sinking velocity depth profiles**

402 Our results show a clear increase of SV with depth, which agrees with the observations across
403 the North Atlantic (Villa-Alfageme et al., 2016a, 2014). Moreover, it supports the implicit
404 assumption when fitting a power-law function to particle flux profiles (Martin et al., 1987), which
405 appears to be one of the best mathematical description of particle flux profiles in the ocean (e.g.
406 Gloege et al., 2017). The power-law fit implies that either particle degradation decreases with
407 depth and/or SVs increase with depth.

408 The observed increase in bulk SVs (i.e. average SV of all sinking particles) with depth is likely
409 due to a combination of several processes that take place simultaneously, including repackaging
410 of smaller, slower sinking particles into faster sinking faecal paellets by zooplankton and fish
411 (Turner, 2015), preferential consumption of low-density compounds such as lipids and faster
412 remineralization rate of smaller particles compared to larger particles (Cavan et al., 2017). The
413 relative importance of each process depends not only on the community, but also on the stage of
414 the bloom. Yet, we propose here that the key of the increasing SV with depth is the fact that slow-
415 sinking particles are remineralized shallower because they are slower. This is because the
416 probability of a particle of being remineralized, depends on the time it spends in the water and
417 slow particles require longer times than fast particles to cover the same depth. Hence, the slowest
418 particles are lost much shallower, while the faster particles can penetrate much deeper into the
419 water column. As a result, the attenuation of the slow-sinking particles is larger than the
420 attenuation of fast particles. This differential behaviour means that the particles that reach deeper
421 depths will sink, on average, faster. Consequently, larger aggregates and faecal pellets that sink
422 fast are most likely to contribute to the deep fluxes, leading to an overall increase in bulk SVs
423 with depth.

424 The three binned average velocities in the mesopelagic zone (100 - 120 m d⁻¹) are slightly lower
425 than the individual SVs (240 - 350 m d⁻¹) associated with the dominant class size of faecal pellets
426 (0.008-0.009 mm³), which contributed up to 66% of total POC flux in the sediment trap at 1950
427 m depth during Nov and Dec 2017 (Manno et al., this issue). This observation is coherent with
428 the hypothesis of an increase in SV with depth due to the shallower remineralization of smaller
429 particles, which hence do not reach the deeper depths.

430 Note that SV and remineralization rate are two interconnected parameters. Microbial degradation
431 and fragmentation directly influence SVs since they alter both size and density, which in turn
432 determine SV. Yet, the SV of very fast particles, such as dense faecal pellets, may remain
433 relatively constant throughout the mesopelagic zone as their fast SVs mean that they “spend less
434 time in the water” and hence “escape” remineralization (Villa-Alfageme et al., 2016a). This idea
435 is supported by the observation that many particles collected at the deep sediment trap (at 1950
436 m depth) were intact or only partially degraded (Manno et al., this issue).

437
438 Though an increase of SV with depth was hypothesised decades ago (Berelson, 2002; Kriest and
439 Oschlies, 2008), several attempts to detect an increase in SV failed, and SV depth profiles,
440 measured using underwater cameras, in different ecosystems did not correlated with depth
441 (Iversen et al., 2010; Lee et al., 2009; Sternberg et al., 1999). Yet, recent work using radioactive
442 pairs (Villa-Alfageme et al., 2016a), has found a distinct pattern of bulk SV increasing with
443 depth, consistent with this study. The enhanced ability of our SV methods to detect systematic
444 changes with depth may be due to the differing scales of integration vs. previous in-situ and ex-
445 situ measurements of individual particles. The ²¹⁰Po-derived SV estimates rely on flux
446 measurements that integrate over weeks to months and all sinking particles, including potentially
447 rare particles with sinking velocities much higher than the mean and which contribute strongly
448 to POC flux. In addition, bulk SV estimates integrate over the complete velocity spectrum,
449 including slow particles. If the contribution of slow sinking particles decreases with depth, as
450 they are remineralized from the water column while sinking, the bulk SV will increase with
451 depth. These combined factors should make this method especially sensitive to changes in SV
452 with depth. Our glider-based bulk SV estimates exclude smaller particles (<100 μm) and hence
453 fail to account fully for slower sinking particles that are less likely to generate clear pulses that
454 can be tracked with depth. Glider-based estimates do not integrate as far in time as the
455 radionuclide pair technique, but do integrate over a broad area (12 km triangle).

456 Rather than a constant increase in SVs with depth, we observed a step change at around 150 m
457 depth from 0.6 m d⁻¹ per meter (surface to 150 m depth; Figure 5b) to 0.1 m d⁻¹ per meter (150 –
458 450 m depth; Figure 5b), indicating two distinct regions of particle processing. These zones agree
459 with the observations that most of the mechanisms affecting particle SVs, except for
460 disaggregation and fragmentation, have a stronger impact in the Euphotic Zone and upper
461 Twilight Zone, where remineralization is more intense (e.g. Giering et al., 2014) likely because
462 temperature, microbial abundance and zooplankton abundance are higher.

463 We suggest that, at P3, the rapid increase in bulk SV in the upper 150 m was caused by an active
464 food web in, and just below, the Z_p. In this zone, the processes that lead to the formation of

465 sinking aggregates are prevalent: phytoplankton grows, aggregate formation and collision. In
466 addition, mesozooplankton (>330 μm) ingestion was highest in this zone (Cook et al., this issue),
467 which is likely indicative of the repackaging of smaller particles into faster sinking faecal pellets.
468 The upper 150 m likely include a greater concentration of slow-sinking particles that do not
469 penetrate far beyond the mixed layer (see also discussion by Giering et al. 2014).

470 Below this active zone, the increase in bulk SVs may have slowed down as the production of
471 fast-sinking particles may have become less frequent as plankton growth is likely negligible
472 owing to the lack of light, the concentration of particles that could collide decreased (Burd and
473 Jackson, 2009), and the abundance of zooplankton that could produce fast sinking pellets
474 decreased (Cook et al., this issue). At the same time, fragmentation processes likely started to
475 become more dominant (e.g. Briggs et al., 2020a). Though remineralization by microbes also
476 decreased (Rayne et al., this issue), the net effect could explain the observed slow-down in the
477 increase of bulk SVs with depth.

478

479 **4.3. Particle sinking velocity progression during an austral diatom bloom**

480 A typical spring diatom bloom is expected to be linked to fast sinking particles formed by
481 phytoplankton aggregation processes. This link is due to high concentrations of diatom cells that
482 trigger the formation of larger aggregates that sink faster than individual cells (De La Rocha and
483 Passow, 2007; Villa-Alfageme et al., 2016a; Zetsche et al., 2020). However, our results indicate
484 that SV during the spring bloom is not constant, and its value depends on the stage of the bloom.

485 In 2017, during COMICS I, phytoplankton size distribution ranged from 0 - 80 μm equivalent
486 spherical diameter, including high concentrations of diatom chains and a lower concentration of
487 dinoflagellates (Poulton, personal communication). This size range is consistent with diatoms
488 previously observed in the Scotia Sea, which typically have cell diameters between ~ 2 to >20
489 μm (Korb et al., 2012). Applying Stokes' equation to estimate diatom SV of the particle
490 distribution in COMICS I, we expect SVs to range from <1 to ~ 50 m d^{-1} . These estimates agree
491 well with our SV measured within the surface ocean (always lower than 50 m d^{-1} , Figure 5 and
492 Table 1).

493 During the diatom bloom, in 2013, average SV at Z_p depth (100 to 225 m d^{-1}) were significantly
494 higher than in 2017 (Figure 2), but agreed with those measured for fast-sinking aggregates
495 (Belcher et al., 2017). SV of > 200 m d^{-1} are also typical for individual aggregates formed and
496 measured in the laboratory (e.g Zetsche et al., 2020). We hence suggest that aggregation
497 processes during the bloom were responsible for the high SV observed in 2013.

498 In the 2012 season, our SV measurements were made well into the post-bloom period, and
499 resulting SV were the lowest of the velocities reported for P3 across the three different spring
500 blooms. At this final stage of the bloom no aggregates were observed (Cavan et al., 2015), likely
501 because cell concentrations, and hence aggregation potential, in the upper ocean are low. FPs
502 were also negligible due to the declined concentration of zooplankton (Le Moigne et al., 2016;
503 Manno et al., 2015). Previous studies in South Georgia described that the flux at the end of the

504 diatom spring bloom was mainly comprised by fewer and smaller-sized diatom cells (Korb et al.,
505 2012), or diatom resting spores, associated with nutrient limitation at the end of a diatom bloom
506 (Cavan et al., 2019; Rembauville et al., 2016). Hence, the low SVs observed during this phase of
507 the bloom are consistent with the expected ecosystem shifts.

508

509 **4.4. Particle sinking velocity as a driver of export efficiency**

510 In north South Georgia we observe that the variability in export efficiency at P3 during the austral
511 spring bloom can be ascribed to the velocity at which particles are exported from the productive
512 layer (Figure 6). Our hypothesis that slow-sinking particles are more easily remineralized in the
513 Euphotic Zone because they spend more time in the zone than the faster particles (Section 4.2;
514 Buesseler et al., 2007) seems to also apply here. The strong influence of particle SV on the
515 relative amount of carbon export out of the productive layer is most probably related to the fact
516 that SV determines the time a sinking particle spends in the Euphotic Zone. The resulting
517 relatively higher degradation of slow-sinking particles in the Euphotic Zone, in comparison to
518 fast-sinking particles, leads to a rapid loss of the slow-sinking particles from this pool compared
519 to fast-sinking particles. As a result, in a community dominated by slow-sinking particles,
520 remineralization will likely occur in the Euphotic Zone leaving less material for export to the
521 Twilight Zone.

522 In terms of carbon sequestration we hypothesize that as slow particles are degraded while sinking
523 they become more refractory. Thus once they exit the active zone their degradation rate is much
524 lower than that of the flux-dominant faster particles, still available for degradation (as described
525 in Section 4.2). In a contrasting scenario such as a nutrient-deficient subtropical gyre dominated
526 by small phytoplankton, the attenuation of carbon flux, governed by slow-sinking particles, is
527 substantial within the Euphotic Zone, accompanied by a concomitantly low *ExpEff*. Conversely,
528 within the Twilight Zone of these subtropical environments, the total carbon flux attenuation,
529 primarily influenced by refractory particles, would be lower than the attenuation observed in the
530 South Georgia conditions analyzed here, where fast particles are prevalent. Unfortunately, the
531 data we have obtained from this cruise are not sufficient to validate this theoretical framework
532 and further evidence is needed to support it.

533 As *ExpEff* is a key metric of the ocean's biological carbon pump that quantifies the fraction of
534 phytoplankton primary production that sinks below the sunlit layer of the ocean, our simple
535 correlation should have a direct impact in its parameterization in a global context. Further
536 investigations are required to analyse if this is specific to describe the functioning of the BCP in
537 north South Georgia or if it can be globally applied.

538

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546

547 **TABLES.**

548 **Table 1.** POC downward flux in $\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$ and Average Sinking Velocities (SV) in m d^{-1}
 549 depth profiles derived from ^{210}Po - ^{210}Pb disequilibrium measured during P3A (15th Nov – 22th
 550 Nov), P3B (29th Nov – 5th Dec) and P3C (9th Dec – 15th Dec). Second columns under Po-
 551 derived flux and SV correspond to the uncertainties, obtained through propagation of
 552 uncertainties from the measurement of ^{210}Po .
 553

	Depth	POC flux- ^{210}Po derived ($\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$)		POC flux-glider derived ($\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$)		SV - ^{210}Po derived (m d^{-1})		SV - glider derived (m d^{-1})
			$\pm \sigma$	Min	Max		$\pm \sigma$	Depth
P3A	10	5.5	3.1	247	1301	14.0	5.9	100 80 115
	50	62	58			30.0	4.1	
	100	358	144			57.6	39.8	
	150	56	38			186.4	57.8	
	175							
	245							
	250	96	86			124.2	40.9	
	350	182	134					
518								
P3B	10	-9.2	3.7	147	1086	16.3	3.6	95 131 64
	50	42	35			30.7	4.9	
	75	75	49			36.9	5.9	
	100	153	39			55.5	10.6	
	150	217	60	126.1	17.2			
	250	336	145	110.6	28.7			
	255							
	458							
P3C	10	52.6	24.7	112	940	29.5	7.7	56 127
	50	187	57			68.0	15.3	
	75	226	70			48.7	11.0	
	100	345	91			43.7	9.1	
	140							
	150	211	57	50.2	10.6			
	250	163	67					
	260							
350	-81	43						

554

555

556 **FIGURE CAPTIONS:**

557 **Figure 1.** Map of North South Georgia and new primary production, NPP ($\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$) during
558 P3A, P3B and P3C periods

559 **Figure 2.** Values of SV (m d^{-1}) vs DOY during three different blooms measured at P3 in 2012
560 (blue), 2013 (green) and 2017 (red) at the base of the Euphotic Zone (Z_p). SV values are derived
561 from radioactive disequilibrium (^{210}Po - ^{210}Pb and ^{234}Th - ^{238}U) and gliders datasets. NPP obtained
562 from satellite images is also included during the three bloom periods. The grey hatch corresponds
563 to COMICS I occupation.

564 **Figure 3.** POC downward flux collected every five days using a rotating sediment trap moored
565 at 1950 m during 2017, provided by (figure adapted from Manno et al. (this issue)). The grey
566 hatch corresponds to COMICS I occupation. The sediment trap was deployed on the mooring in
567 P3, as part of the Ecosystems programme at the British Antarctic Survey (BAS) and the Scotia
568 Sea Open Ocean Laboratories (SCOOBIES) sustained observation programme at the BAS.
569 Results from 2012 and 2013 are included, together with NPP obtained from satellite images
570 during the 2017 bloom period.

571 **Figure 4.** POC downward flux in $\text{mg m}^{-2} \text{d}^{-1}$ derived from ^{210}Po - ^{210}Pb disequilibrium measured
572 during P3A (15th Nov – 22th Nov), P3B (29th Nov – 5th Dec) and P3C (9th Dec – 15th
573 Dec). Uncertainties are obtained from standard deviation and error propagation and correspond
574 to 1σ .

575 **Figure 5.** Average sinking velocities (SV) in m d^{-1} depth profiles. 5a) shows SVs obtained from
576 ^{210}Po - ^{210}Pb disequilibrium and from gliders. 5b) shows average (full circles), maximum and
577 minimum (grey lines outlining the hatch) sinking velocities depth profiles calculated using the
578 data points from the two methods (showed in Figure 5a) at each depth. Broken lines correspond
579 to the linear fitting of the average values from surface to 150 m and from 150 to 450 m.

580 **Figure 6.** Sinking velocities derived from ^{210}Po - ^{210}Pb disequilibrium (Bloom of years 2013 and
581 2017) and ^{234}Th - ^{238}U disequilibrium (bloom of year 2012) versus Export Efficiency calculated
582 as the ratio POC flux at the base of the Euphotic Zone (Z_p). The linear fitting of the complete
583 dataset is included

584

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